

Speculative analysis of the spin and nature of electrons

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Abstract

To analyze the concept of spin, the article begins with the initial historical hypothesis of the electron's rotational motion and the subsequent criticisms raised by Wolfgang Pauli against this idea. Pauli argued that for an electron to produce the required angular momentum through rotational motion, it would need to spin at a speed exceeding the speed of light, which is not physically possible.

Building on this critique, the article introduces an idealized mathematical model based on classical and relativistic theories, where the electron's tangential velocity is instead set equal to the speed of light. This hypothetical framework enables a speculative analysis of the electron's nature, particularly regarding its mass and intrinsic properties.

Keywords: Spin, Fine-Structure Constant, Electron Mass, Antimatter, Spacetime, Dark Energy

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1 Introduction: Spin as the Self-Rotation of the Electron

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The physical interpretation of the quantum degree of freedom known as spin was formalized by Samuel Goudsmit and George Uhlenbeck in 1925. The concept, however, was anticipated by Ralph Kronig, who proposed in 1925 that spin could be explained as the self-rotation of electrons. Upon reviewing

Kronig's hypothesis, Wolfgang Pauli sharply criticized it¹, arguing that for the electron to generate the required angular momentum through self-rotation, it would need to spin faster than the speed of light. This, Pauli pointed out, would violate the theory of relativity.

2 Classical Electron Radius and Spin

The classical electron radius is a physical constant.

This constant is derived by considering the electron in a classical (i.e., not described by quantum mechanics) and relativistic theory². Specifically, assuming the electron as a sphere with charge e and radius r_e its electrostatic energy is of the order of:

$$E = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{r_e} \quad (1)$$

From a relativistic point of view, the energy is:

$$E = m_e c^2 \quad (2)$$

with m_e being the mass of the electron.

Equating the equations (1) and (2), the value of r_e is found:

$$r_e = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{m_e c^2} = 2,8179403267 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m} \quad (3)$$

The radius thus calculated is so small that if one incorrectly considers spin as an angular momentum produced by the rotation of electrons, as predicted by Lorentz, the peripheral velocity of the electron would have to exceed the speed of light.

In the following discussion, however, purely for mathematical purposes, we will hypothesize what could happen if the electron had a peripheral velocity exactly equal to the speed of light.

According to Kronig's thesis, at this point, consider the spin S as generated by the angular momentum M of the electron. Given the units of measurement for spin, a dimensionless constant k can be introduced, equal to the ratio of these two quantities:

$$k = \frac{M}{S} \quad (4)$$

As is well known, the smallest possible spin value S of the electron is given by:

$$S = \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad (5)$$

Assuming the charge is entirely concentrated at a point on the surface, the angular momentum M of the electron can instead be derived from the product of the momentum p and the radius r :

$$M = pr \quad (6)$$

The momentum p can, in turn, be derived from the energy equation:

$$pc = m_e c^2 \quad (7)$$

By combining equations 4, 5, 6, and 7, one obtains:

$$\frac{k\hbar}{2m_e c} = r \quad (8)$$

Equating the two radii (3) and (8) thus calculated, leads to:

$$\frac{k\hbar}{2m_e c} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{m_e c^2} \quad (9)$$

which can be simplified to:

$$k = 2\alpha \quad (10)$$

where α is the fine-structure constant.

Using this last equation, the angular momentum of the electron M can thus be calculated:

$$M = 2\alpha \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad (11)$$

Simplifying this last formula, the important relation is deduced:

$$M = \alpha\hbar \quad (12)$$

That is, the electron's angular momentum is on the order of magnitude of the product of the fine-structure constant and the reduced Planck constant, or equivalently, it is on the order of the fine-structure constant times the value of the spin.

3 Matter and Antimatter

We now attempt to further develop the ideal model discussed in the previous section: let us assume that the electron is not composed of a single rotating particle, but rather of multiple particles. Suppose that, in this case, there is no reason for all particles to be negatively charged, but that some particles are negatively charged while others are positively charged, potentially in unequal numbers.

To this end, we can use the concept of matter and antimatter: particles of matter and antimatter pairs have identical characteristics and energy, but opposite charges^{3,4}. Thus, in our hypothetical model of the electron, composed of multiple particles, we can increase the number of particles with the same charge to realize the total charge and increase the number of particles with equal velocity to enhance the momentum and spin.

We start with a pair consisting of a particle and its antiparticle, both in rotation and with opposite charge e . It is clear that the overall charge in this case is zero, but since they are in motion, the charges can still generate a non-zero interaction (of a magnetic type) with external particles (which are also assumed to be composed of moving charges) similar to the electric forces generated by the electron itself.

If we consider an overall stationary electron, i.e., with zero momentum, the two particles must have opposite velocities. Given r as the distance between the two charges, the potential energy due to the electrostatic force of the system is:

$$E_e = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{r} \quad (13)$$

Let's now calculate the magnetic interaction of the pair, starting with the two formulas that allow us to compute the magnetic field \vec{B} generated by the first particle moving with \vec{v} velocity on the second and the corresponding attractive force:

$$\vec{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{e\vec{v} \times \vec{u}_r}{r^2} \quad (14)$$

$$\vec{F} = e\vec{v} \times \vec{B} \quad (15)$$

where \vec{u}_r is the unit vector pointing from the first charge to the second (it should be noted that these formulas are valid for velocities much lower than the speed of light).

The velocities of the two particles can be oriented in any direction, as long as they are opposite to each other. However, from equations 14 and 15, it can be seen that the field and the force attain their maximum values when \vec{v} is orthogonal to \vec{u}_r as shown in the following figure:

Fig. 1 Movement of Particle and Antiparticle

In the case shown in the figure, the magnitude of the magnetic force, directed from the first charge P^- to the second P^+ is:

$$F = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{v^2 e^2}{r^2} \quad (16)$$

The magnetic potential energy is therefore:

$$E_m = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{v^2 e^2}{r} \quad (17)$$

As the velocities increase, approaching the speed of light (although this limit needs to be re-evaluated considering the validity of equations 14 and 15), equation 17 would tend to:

$$E_m \approx \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{c^2 e^2}{r} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{r} \quad (18)$$

The total electromagnetic energy of the system is therefore:

$$E = E_e + E_m = \frac{2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{r} \quad (19)$$

and it is equal to twice the electrostatic energy of the electron given in equation 1.

At this point, let us calculate the relativistic energy of the two particles, which is given by:

$$E = 2pc \quad (20)$$

Equating equations 19 and 20 results in:

$$\frac{2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{r} = 2pc \quad (21)$$

from which r can be derived:

$$r = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{pc} \quad (22)$$

If we set r equal to the electron radius (equation 3), then the relativistic energy of the individual particle is equal to the relativistic energy of the electron:

$$pc = m_e c^2 \quad (23)$$

While the relativistic energy of the particle pair, that is, of the entire system, is equal to twice the relativistic energy of the electron:

$$2pc = 2m_e c^2 \quad (24)$$

At this point, we introduce a hypothesis: it is known that particle-antiparticle pairs can be generated from the vacuum through quantum fluctuations⁵. In our two-particle model, we have observed that these pairs can reach a maximum electromagnetic energy equal to twice the electromagnetic energy of an electron (see Equation 19). Similarly, they can recombine, releasing a relativistic energy equal to twice the relativistic energy of an electron (see Equation 24). In such a fluctuation, the average values correspond precisely to the electromagnetic and relativistic energies of the electron. However, while it is clear that the electromagnetic energy manifests as a force between particles and towards any surrounding particles, the fate of the relativistic energy generated by the recombination of the matter-antimatter pair remains to be clarified. The hypothesis is that this energy might curve spacetime, thereby generating the well-known gravitational force (and mass) between material particles. This distortion of spacetime and the resulting gravitational force, however, becomes apparent when the particles recombine, i.e., when the electromagnetic field disappears. Essentially, the two fields alternate. We are able to perceive and measure them simultaneously because we observe the average values, but these averages, in turn, obscure the mutually exclusive nature of these forces. For further clarification, the following figure shows the oscillatory trend of relativistic and electromagnetic energies.

Fig. 2 Trends of Relativistic and Electromagnetic Energies

4 Wave and Particle

By interpreting the electron as a collection of particles and antiparticles that separate and then recombine, the very concept of a wave and the frequency associated with the particle becomes tangible—a concept clearly identified by Louis de Broglie at the dawn of quantum mechanics⁶. In this sense, one can

even think of the wave function as a disturbance that separates matter from antimatter, creating point particles that then recombine, transforming into energy. This energy, by deforming space and time, generates mass and the resulting gravitational attraction.

The process then repeats in reverse, allowing the propagation of the disturbance itself. The frequency introduced by de Broglie thus becomes the rate at which spacetime deformation alternates with the presence of two matter and antimatter particles and the resulting electromagnetic field.

5 Spacetime Curvature

The equations of general relativity predict that gravitational attraction and the associated mass (gravitational mass) arise from geometric causes, specifically from a curvature of spacetime that tends to draw surrounding bodies toward it^{7,8}. This curvature is always depicted in physics textbooks as "concave", given its attractive nature. In the previous chapter, we considered the

Fig. 3 Curvature of space time

hypothesis that curvature might be generated by the energy released from the recombination of matter and antimatter. However, we now want to consider the possibility that curvature does not necessarily have to be "concave"—why couldn't it be "convex" and possess a repulsive nature?

Repulsive masses do not exist in nature, but it is conceivable that "concave"-attractive microcurvatures of space could attract each other, creating a larger curvature that is clearly observable, much like the large masses of stars and planets we know. "Convex"-repulsive microcurvatures, if they existed, would instead repel each other and distribute themselves homogeneously throughout space.

Assuming, by a simple principle of symmetry, that there are equal numbers of attractive and repulsive curvatures, there should be a greater number of

repulsive curvatures in empty space, as the attractive ones are concentrated within massive bodies.

We know that current science is studying a phenomenon known as "dark energy," which consists of a hypothetical form of energy that is not directly detectable and is uniformly distributed throughout space. This dark energy might explain, through a significant negative pressure, the accelerated expansion of the universe ⁹ and other experimental evidence.

Thus, we arrive at our second hypothesis: this predominance of repulsive space-time curvatures in the vacuum could justify this hypothetical form of energy and the associated negative pressure present in the vacuum.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis presented in this article proposes an idealized mathematical model of the electron, based on concepts from classical and relativistic theory, which envisions the particle not as a single mass but as a system of matter and antimatter particles rotating relative to each other at the speed of light.

Although purely ideal, this model suggests the possibility of separating the two terms of the special relativity equation, where energy and the product of mass and the square of the speed of light appear equal only in average values but oscillate and interchange over short time intervals.

By extending this explanation to every point in the vacuum, from which matter and antimatter particles can emerge through simple quantum fluctuations, a speculative hypothesis on the origin of dark matter is introduced, offering new perspectives for investigating this enigmatic component of the universe.

Nomenclature

E	Energy
E_e	Electrostatic Energy
E_m	Magnetic Energy
ϵ_0	Permittivity of Free Space Constant
e	Electron Charge
r_e	Classical Electron Radius
m_e	Electron mass
c	Speed of Light
M	Angular Momentum
S	Spin
k	Ratio between Angular Momentum and Spin
\hbar	Reduced Planck Constant
p	Momentum
α	Fine-Structure Constant
μ_0	Vacuum Permeability Constant
\vec{B}	Magnetic Field Vector
\vec{F}	Magnetic Force Vector
\vec{u}_r	Radial Unit Vector
\vec{v}	Velocity Vector
v	Magnituse of the Velocity Vector

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